

PREDIABETES: CURRENT STATE OF THE PROBLEM**Kodirova Nargizakhon Umarovna**Assistant of the Department of Propedeutics of internal diseases of
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ABSTRACT

Impaired glucose tolerance and impaired fasting glucose are early carbohydrate metabolism disorders, the prevalence of which in Russia and worldwide is growing annually. These conditions subsequently lead to the development of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Prediabetes is of particular interest today due to its diagnostic criteria and developmental mechanisms. Overweight and obesity often underlie the development of early carbohydrate metabolism disorders. Prediabetes leads to early cardiovascular risks, atherosclerotic vascular lesions, and severe complications such as acute coronary artery disease and heart failure. Particular attention today is needed not only to assess glycemic control indicators as a screening tool for prediabetes, but also to assess body mass index and waist circumference, hip circumference, and their ratio are particularly relevant. Understanding the diagnostic criteria for prediabetes, the mechanisms of its development, identifying risk groups, and knowing about possible pathogenetic therapies will enable timely detection and practical implementation of lifestyle modification recommendations and drug therapy, preventing or delaying the onset of type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular diseases.

Prediabetes is an early carbohydrate metabolism disorder that precedes the development of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), in which glycemic levels are already above normal but have not yet reached T2DM levels [1]. Prediabetes includes any of the early carbohydrate metabolism disorders, such as impaired fasting glucose (IFG) and impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) [2].

Worldwide, there are approximately 352.1 million people with impaired glucose tolerance. By 2045, the number of people with IGT aged 20-79 years is expected to increase to 587 million, representing 8.3% of the adult population [1]. NATION, the first national epidemiological cross-sectional study of the prevalence of T2DM in the Russian Federation, showed that early carbohydrate metabolism disorders, such as IGT and NGT, were recorded in 19.3% (approximately 20.7 million) of the Russian adult population aged 20-79 years [3].

According to various studies, IGT is particularly important in carbohydrate metabolism. For example, according to the DECODE study, which presented the results of 10 European cohort studies including more than 22,000 patients, increased mortality was recorded among patients with IGT detected by a glucose tolerance test, while the correlation between the changes no association between fasting plasma glucose levels and mortality was observed [4].

The role of obesity in the development of early carbohydrate metabolism disorders is currently being actively discussed. Carbohydrate metabolism disorders occur in more than half of obese patients. Obesity has become one of the most important medical and social problems in the modern world, as it is highly prevalent and requires significant financial expenditures for the treatment of obesity-related diseases. The prevalence of overweight and obesity in the Russian Federation is 59.2% and 24.1%, respectively. According to data from the ESSE-RF multicenter observational study (covering 11 regions) which included 25,224 individuals aged 25-64 years, the prevalence of obesity in the population was 29.7%. Obesity is a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD) and type 2 diabetes (according to the WHO, overweight and obesity underlie the development of up to 44-57% of all cases of type 2 diabetes).

The likelihood of developing diabetes mellitus in the future is significantly higher in individuals with obesity and IGT. Annual conversion of IGT to diabetes mellitus occurs in 5-10% of patients and in 20-34% over a 5-year period, with a 38-65% increase in the case of a combination of IGT and IGT [5].

Today, accumulated data indicate that prediabetes significantly increases the risk of developing not only diabetes mellitus but also cardiovascular diseases at all stages of the cardiovascular continuum from endothelial dysfunction to heart failure (HF). The prevalence of T2DM among patients with CVD was found to be 8-14%, and prediabetes to be 14.6-36.4%, which was higher than similar rates in the population obtained in the NATION study—5.4% and 19.3% for T2DM and prediabetes, respectively [6]. A 14-year follow-up of 11,057 individuals who did not have T2DM at baseline demonstrated a 40% increased risk of developing heart failure in patients with prediabetic HbA1c levels (6.0-6.5%) compared to individuals with normoglycemia [7]. However, despite the aforementioned risks, there is low awareness among specialists regarding prediabetes and T2DM. Interesting data were obtained in the PARADIGM-FH study, which showed that among 8,274 patients with systolic heart failure, only 35% had a history of type 2 diabetes. A pre-study screening identified an additional 13% of patients with type 2 diabetes (HbA1c >6.5%) and 25% with prediabetes (HbA1c 6.0-6.4%). This means that 38% of patients who developed heart failure with a left ventricular ejection fraction $\leq 40\%$ had not been promptly diagnosed with clinically significant carbohydrate metabolism disorders (prediabetes and type 2 diabetes) [8].

Thus, all of the data presented indicate that prediabetes induces the development of serious diseases and conditions that significantly worsen the patient's quality of life and prognosis. Risk factors and screening The NATION study demonstrated a correlation between carbohydrate metabolism disorders and age, body mass index (BMI), sedentary lifestyle, and arterial hypertension [3].

Thus, the main risk factors for the development of T2DM were identified: prediabetes, age over 45 years, overweight and obesity, and a positive family history of Diabetes mellitus,

low physical activity, history of gestational diabetes mellitus or large fetus, arterial hypertension ($\geq 140/90$ mmHg or drug-based antihypertensive therapy), HDL cholesterol ≤ 0.9 mmol/L and/or triglyceride levels ≥ 2.82 mmol/L, polycystic ovary syndrome, and the presence of cardiovascular disease.

Screening to detect early carbohydrate metabolism disorders, such as IGT and NGT, should be performed by all patients over the age of 45, as well as overweight patients of any age with one of the risk factors [2].

Given the role of obesity in the development of early carbohydrate metabolism disorders, the characteristics of fat distribution are currently being actively studied using computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging.

Based on the data obtained, adipose tissue is divided into visceral (intra-abdominal) and subcutaneous. It is the increased amount of intra-abdominal fat that is often associated with hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance, which underlies the development of early carbohydrate metabolism disorders. The distribution of adipose tissue in the body is assessed using the patient's waist-to-hip ratio (WC/HR), measured with a tape measure. If this ratio exceeds 1.0 in men and 0.8 in women, abdominal obesity is considered present. A 10-fold increased risk of diabetes has been observed in individuals with high WC values compared to those with the lowest WC values. Based on an analysis of a number of large prospective epidemiological studies in various populations (European and Asian) across various age groups, notable conclusions were reached. Abdominal obesity, assessed by WC and WC/HR ratio, is associated with an increased risk of death from any cause across the entire range of BMI values. Overall, both WC and WC/HR ratio are more significant markers of all-cause mortality risk than BMI. This is especially true for older individuals, who often exhibit an inverse association between BMI and mortality. According to the authors, WC can replace both BMI and WC/HR ratio as a marker of all-cause mortality risk [9, 10]. In 2015, the prospective Framingham Study assessed visceral and subcutaneous fat content using multidetector computed tomography. The sample included 3,324 obese patients. It was demonstrated that every 1 SD of excess adipose tissue volume was associated with an increase in overall mortality, as well as cancer-related mortality. The study authors concluded that the identified relationship was due to systemic inflammation caused by high levels of macrophages, proinflammatory cytokines, and extracellular matrix fibrosis [11].

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